

The Clerk to the Committee
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
Office of Parliament
Osu- Accra

RE: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

This memorandum is in response to a request from the Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs. They have asked for a written memorandum from the general public with regards to the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021* as published in the Daily Guide newspaper on [September 9, 2021](#). Thank you for the opportunity to submit this memorandum to assist the committee in its review of and deliberation on the bill.

I am urging the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs to **drop** the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021*. At its core, the bill is homophobic, transphobic, queerphobic, and it goes against the human rights of Ghanaians. The bill will lead to horrible and disastrous consequences for queer and trans Ghanaians who already face extreme violence within Ghanaian society. Under this bill, the state will be justified in incarcerating, and promoting increased levels of harm against LGBTQIA+ Ghanaians.

The *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021* promotes conversion therapy, which has been found to cause harmful psychological damage to queer people. It also forces intersex people to undergo sexual reassignment surgery which strips intersex people of their bodily autonomy and promotes the erroneous idea of biological essentialism. It criminalizes advocacy of LGBTQIA+ rights which is a human rights offense and goes against freedom of speech. Laws should be created to **protect** the rights and humanity of LGBTQIA+ people as recommended by human rights groups.

I am a concerned Ghanaian living in the diaspora and I want to see LGBTQIA+ Ghanaians live a full, free life without the constraints of state-sanctioned homophobia, transphobia, and queerphobia promoted in the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021*. Thus I oppose this bill and I'm urging it to **not be passed**.

Sincerely,
A Concerned Ghanaian